

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPMENT OF METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: One of the ways that the teacher's pedagogical skill has a significant impact on the increase of his qualification, pedagogical ability, pedagogical competence is to improve the qualifications of continuous professional education. This article talks about professional competencies, methodical competence, its components, tasks of methodical competence and how to form this competence in primary school teachers.

Key words: competence, professional competence, methodical competence, method, tool, qualification, activity criterion.

Introduction.

In the conditions where the methodical competence of future elementary school teachers in our country is constantly changing, having studied the advanced foreign experiences, developing the technology, didactic foundations, pedagogical conditions for the development of their methodical competence in the higher educational institution, content and structure, improvement criteria and levels of formation, form, method, tools, model, increasing the effectiveness of teaching quality, as well as the theoretical and practical foundations of the development of methodical competence in future elementary school teachers in a pedagogical higher educational institution development is important.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

The expected result in the process of teaching students in pedagogic higher education institutions is formed in the form of requirements for mastering the basic educational programs presented through general cultural, general professional and professional competencies. The profile (specialty) competence of the future teacher is also defined in the state educational standards, which is an important component of the teacher's professional competence. Currently, it is one of the most understudied problems. One of such issues is to determine a competent approach to the development of professional competencies in future primary school teachers and to develop its structural model in accordance with the main provisions of the State Education Standards. In order to determine the professional competence of the future elementary school teacher, we will focus on some studies devoted to the study of this concept. In the studies where professional competence is studied as a pedagogical problem, the teacher's characteristics are mainly analyzed.

V.I. Baydenko described the concept of "professional competence" as follows:

- to have the knowledge, skills, qualifications and abilities necessary to work in one's specialty, to have the characteristics of autonomy and flexibility at the same time in partially solving professional problems;
- development of cooperation with colleagues in a professional interpersonal environment;

- the design structure of the standards, including the performance criterion (quality measure), the field of application, and the required knowledge;
- effective use of abilities that allow effective implementation of professional activities according to the requirements of the employer;
- an integrated combination of knowledge, characteristics and skills that allow a person to successfully perform work in the modern work environment [2, 72].

Summarizing the above, V.I.Baydenko understands professional competence as the readiness and ability to act in accordance with the requirements of the activity, to independently solve issues and problems, and at the same time to be able to evaluate the results of one's activity, that is, appropriate skills, technical methods.

O.V. According to Hovov, professional competence is not only competence, i.e. professional competence as work experience, skills and knowledge, but also social-communicative and individual abilities that ensure independence in professional activity [5, 454- 455].

Yu.G. Tatur and V.Ye. The Medvedevs define the competence of a future specialist as the desire and ability to demonstrate one's potential (knowledge, skills, experience, personal qualities, etc.) defined as the willingness to use all one's capabilities (knowledge, skills, experience and personal qualities) to be able to work successfully in any field and to be consciously aware of the responsibility for its result.

G.A. According to Larionova, the structure of readiness includes a complex of practical knowledge and characteristics that ensure the entry into activity of a person. Preparation for work is complex, consisting of two components, i.e. operational (knowledge and skills) and personal (instructions, work orientation, professional motive characteristics, system of habits and relationships, emotional and volitional functions, professionally important qualities of a person). system [3, 171].

Determining what the specialist has competencies, i.e., what method of activity he can master, what he can do, what he is ready for, is called a competent approach. One of the conceptually important ways to manage the quality of training of graduates of a higher educational institution is to implement a competent approach to the modernization of the content of professional education.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The problem of increasing the level of professional competence of a future teacher who has the ability to think freely and actively, to model the educational process, to develop and implement new ideas and technologies of teaching and upbringing, is a modern socio-economic problem. is relevant in the circumstances.

The main conditions for the development of professional competence of future teachers are as follows:

- 1) organizational and managerial ability (*curriculum, educational process graph, lesson schedule, development of criteria for determining the level of competence, material and technical support of the educational process*);
- 2) educational and methodological (*choosing the content of classes, integration of different courses, separation of leading ideas*);
- 3) technological (*control-evaluation, organization of active forms of education, identification of groups of knowledge included in competence, application of innovative technologies*);

4) psychological-pedagogical (*diagnosing the development of students, encouraging motivation to teach, determining the criteria of competence, directing students to work in cooperation*).

The structure of the future teacher's professional competence is determined through his pedagogical skills, and skills (knowledge based on theoretical knowledge and oriented towards solving pedagogical problems) are determined through a set of gradually developing actions.

CONCLUSION.

Today, in the process of implementing the requirements of the "Law on Education" [1], the training of highly qualified pedagogues is being put on the agenda as an important issue. Therefore, based on these requirements, the training of knowledgeable, independent thinkers, creative seekers, highly qualified, cultured people in various fields is one of the urgent problems. Among the conditions that guarantee the development of a person in the new model recognized by the law, his development as a possessor of deep knowledge, and the conditions that guarantee his perfection, the methods and rules of psychology are sufficient to apply the teacher's professional-methodical competence to the processes of education and training. as if not. Accordingly, starting with the development trends during the education period of the young generation, studying how the learner's assimilation of new teaching technologies affects his mental and intellectual abilities, and didactic methods in psychology. requires coordination with methods. For this, a future teacher is required to have a high level of methodological competence, especially social-psychological competence related to the ability to correctly assess the psychology of learners and teachers in different conditions.

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